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Research Article

**HEPATITIS B & C SCREENING IN SURGICAL UNIT-II OF
HOLY FAMILY HOSPITAL RAWALPINDI****Dr. Sadia Nazir¹, Dr. Ammar Farooq², Dr. Jawad Ahmad Khan³**¹ Al Nafees Medical College and Hospital Islamabad² Mohtarma Benazir Bhutto Shaheed Medical College, Mirpur AJK³ KMU Institute of Medical Sciences, Kohat**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:****Aim:** To know the prevalence of HBsAg and anti-HCV and to assess risk factors**Project:** A prospective descriptive study**Place and Duration:** In the Surgical Unit-II of Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi for one-year duration from May 2019 to May 2020.**Patients:** Patients of both genders older than 13 years of age undergoing elective surgery**Methodology:** Screening for HBsAg and Anti HCV was performed in all patients with the Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) test in the preoperative period. The information was recorded on a pre-designed form that included the current and previous hepatitis profile, risk factors, vaccination history along with demographics.**Results:** A total of 1,185 patients underwent elective surgery during the study period. In total, there were 580 (48.9%) men and 605 (51.1%) women. 35 patients (2.9%) were HBsAg positive, 170 patients (14.3%) tested positive for anti-HCV antibodies, while none of them tested positive for both HBsAg and anti-HCV.**Conclusion:** The number of patients suffering from hepatitis B and C is very large. Screening for HBsAg and Anti HCV should be mandatory in all patients undergoing surgery.**Keywords:** Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C, surgery**Corresponding author:****Dr. Sadia Nazir,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Viral hepatitis is one of the major health problems worldwide. Hepatitis B and C are one of the most common causes of chronic liver disease and liver failure¹⁻². The acute phase of both diseases with malaise, anorexia, fever, abdominal pain mainly in the right hypochondrium and epigastric region, and jaundice³⁻⁴. Chronic disease leads to complications such as esophageal varices, ascites, hepatic encephalopathy and finally a malignant tumor. Hepatitis B was first isolated in 1963, while hepatitis C was first cloned in 1989. It is estimated that nearly 600 million people worldwide are infected with the hepatitis C virus⁵⁻⁶. Both hepatitis B and hepatitis C are commonly transmitted through contaminated blood, and as little as 0.01 ml can transmit the infection. Fortunately, vaccinations against hepatitis B are available, which are an important part of the vaccination schedule around the world, and this is why the incidence of hepatitis B is on a downward trend⁷⁻⁸. The aim of the study was to assess the stage of the disease in hospitalized surgical patients and to assess risk factors.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The study was conducted at the Surgical Unit-II of Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi for one-year duration from May 2019 to May 2020. All patients admitted to elective surgery were included in the study. Patients under the age of 13 and those who came in in an accident or emergency were excluded

from the study. In the preoperative period, all patients were tested with the ELISA test for HBsAg and Anti HCV. All patients were asked about disease symptoms, risk factors and vaccination history. All this information, along with demographic data, was recorded on a specially designed proforma.

RESULTS:

A total of 1,185 patients were screened, including 580 men (48.9%) and 605 women (51.1%). A total of 205 patients (17.3%) were positive for hepatitis B or C, of which 35 patients (3%) were positive for hepatitis B and 170 patients (14%) were positive for hepatitis C. 80% of all patients with hepatitis B and 69% of all patients with hepatitis C were under 40 years of age. Of the 35 patients with hepatitis B, 25 (71.4%) are male and 10 (28.6%) are female, while out of 170 patients with hepatitis C, 90 (52.9%) are male and 80 (47.1) are women. Of the total number of 980 negative patients, 465 (47.4%) are men and 515 (52.5%) are women. Of the positive patients with both hepatitis B and C, most of the patients had more than 2 risk factors and were hospitalized, had surgery, blood transfusion, and dental procedures. All patients in the study were asked about their vaccination status, but surprisingly only 11 patients (0.92%) were vaccinated against hepatitis B. Most patients simply did not know about the vaccination.

Figure 1: Patients in the study on the basis of age groups

Table 1: Hepatitis B and C positive patients in the study on the basis of age groups

Age group in years	Total			Hepatitis B Positive			Hepatitis C Positive		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
13-20	80	97	177	7	3	10	10	6	17
21-30	187	178	365	8	4	12	22	21	43
31-40	169	127	296	4	2	6	31	27	58
41-50	111	136	247	4	0	4	18	20	38
51-60	27	43	70	2	1	3	9	6	15
>60 years	6	24	30	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2: Seroprevalence of HBsAg and AntiHCV (n=1185)

	Male	Female	Total
HBsAg +ve	25(71%)	10(29%)	35(3%)
Anti HCV +ve	90(53%)	80(47%)	170(14%)
HBsAg and AntiHCV +ve	0	0	0
HbsAg and AntiHCV -ve	465(47%)	515(53%)	980(83%)

Table 3: Risk factors evaluation

Risk factors	HBsAg +ve	AntiHCV +ve	HBsAg and AntiHCV -ve
History of hospitalization	24	111	239
History of surgery	19	98	184
History of blood transfusion	14	83	135
History of drug abuse	5	9	26
History of dental procedure	29	63	206
History of tatoing	0	0	4
History of ear/nose piercing	5	81	507
History of jaundice	4	26	77
Vaccination against hepatitis b	0	1	10

DISCUSSION:

Hepatitis B and C appear to be endemic in most parts of the world, especially in underdeveloped countries. Much research has been done in Pakistan over the past few years and a number of guidelines have been formulated to control and prevent the spread of the disease, but the number of affected patients continues to grow. In our study, the prevalence of HBsAg and Anti HCV in operated patients was 2.95% and 14.34%, respectively⁹⁻¹⁰. In a study by Zubia Masood et al⁸ in Karachi, the prevalence of HBsAg and AntiHCV was 6.45% and 11.3%, respectively. They are comparable to our study¹¹⁻¹². A study in Japan showed that the incidence of hepatitis B and C viruses was 1.8% and 7.1%, respectively, while another study in Turkey showed that HBsAg was positive at 6.6%. In our study, men and women infected with the hepatitis C virus were almost in equal proportions, with the highest percentages in the third and fourth decades of life, according to a study by Meri et al. In Greece. Transmission of the hepatitis B and C virus is mainly via blood, blood products, contaminated needles and equipment. In our study, history of prior operations was present in 54.2% and 58% of hepatitis B and C

positive patients, respectively¹³⁻¹⁴. Similarly, a history of blood transfusion was present in 41% of patients with hepatitis B and 49% hepatitis C virus positive patients. Both of the above statistics are significantly higher than the 0.01-0.02% reported from the UK and Europe. Contaminated needles and tools can transmit infection for months. The hepatitis B virus is eight times more infectious than HIV. The average risk of hepatitis C transmission following a needle stick injury is approximately 1.8%. In our study, 84% of patients with hepatitis B and 37% of patients who tested positive for hepatitis C reported a dental history¹⁵. Previously, hospitalization affected 68.6% of patients with hepatitis B and 65.3% of patients with hepatitis C. The male population (71%) had a slightly higher incidence in our study, which is comparable to the study in Greece by Meri et al.

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